

Kinetics of Substitution of Aquo-ligands from *cis*-Diaquobisoxalatochromium(III) Ion by Quinolinic Acid in Water—Ethanol Medium

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The kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligand from *cis*-diaquobisoxalatochromium(III) ion by quinolinic acid has been studied spectrophotometrically. The following rate law has been established,

$$\frac{d[\text{Cr(ox)}_2(\text{quinH})^{-2}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{Cr(ox)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] [\text{quinH}^{-1}]$$

in the pH range 2.0–5.9, where k_2 is the second order rate constant. The rate is slow at low pH around 2, increases with increasing pH and reaches a maximum at pH 4.5, then decreases with further increase of pH. The anation rate and activation parameters have been calculated and compared with isotopic water exchange reaction. A reaction mechanism involving S_N^2 path has been suggested.

REPORTS on water replacement reaction of various anionic ligands with stable aquo-complexes of chromium(III) are available in literature. Some authors¹⁻⁴ observed that the reaction rates are independent on the concentration of entering anions and proposed S_N1 mechanism, others⁵⁻¹⁴ interpreted their results implying that bond making plays a significant role in anation reaction as evidenced by the small but definite dependence of the formation rates on the nature and concentration of ligands. Some of them also showed that substitution proceeds through the formation of ion-pair association. Thus despite the large amount of work done on chromium(III) complexes, controversy regarding its mechanism persists. Further, the aquo-ligand substitution in *cis*-diaquobisoxalatochromium(III) ion by pyridine carboxylic acids has not been studied so far. It is therefore planned to study the kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands in $[\text{Cr(ox)}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{-2}$ by several pyridine carboxylic acids. In this paper the results on quinolinic acid are presented.

Experimental

AnalaR grade chemicals were used. *Cis*-K[Cr(C₂O₄)₂(H₂O)₂]2H₂O (Complex-I) was prepared following the reported method¹⁵, and its purity was checked by elemental analysis (Found : Cr, 14.84 ; oxalate, 50.9. Calcd. for : Cr, 15.34 ; oxalate, 51.9%). The complex, *cis*-K[Cr(C₂O₄)₂(H₂O)₂]2H₂O showed maximum absorbance at 416 nm and 562 nm which is concordant with that in literature¹⁶, and ϵ values at the two wavelengths were experimentally determined and found 67.25 (lit. 68.5) and 50.0 (lit. 51.0), respectively. Solutions of quinolinic acid and the complex of desired concentration were prepared by dissolving the calculated amounts in 30%

ethanol. The pH values of the reaction mixtures were adjusted with perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide. A Elico LI 10T pH meter was used for measurement of pH and a Beckman D.B.G. spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Due to high solubility, it was not possible to isolate the product (Complex-II) of the reaction between *cis*-[Cr(ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ and quinolinic acid in pure crystalline form. However, the formation of product in solution was indicated by following absorbance of the reaction mixture, thermostated at 65° for 24 h containing the Complex-I and ligand in ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 5. These solutions show λ_{max} at 400 ($\epsilon=124$) and 550 nm ($\epsilon=90$). Shifting of λ_{max} (from that of Complex-I) towards lower wavelengths and higher value of extinction coefficient indicate the formation of a hetero chelate by quinolinic acid in solution. Composition of the product (1 : 1) in solution was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

Kinetic study · Temperature equilibrated solution of quinolinic acid and the Complex-I of desired concentrations at experimental pH and ionic strength were mixed and the course of the reaction studied by measuring absorbance at 530 nm, where a substantial difference existed in the spectra of the Complexes-I and -II (Fig. 1). Quinolinic acid has no absorbance at this wavelength. The temperature for any set of experiments were thermostatically controlled within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

The pseudo-first order rate constants for the substitution reaction were obtained by plotting $\log(D_\infty - D_0)/(D_\infty - D_t)$ against time, where D_∞ , D_0 and D_t are the absorbance at infinite time, in the beginning and after time t , respectively. The pseudo-first order plots were linear from start to end of the

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra at pH=4.0: (I) $cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^-$ (H_2O) $_2$ 0.005 M, and (II) $cis-[Cr(Ox)_2(H_2O)(OH)]^-$ 0.005 M; quinolinic acid=0.05 M, spectra recorded after keeping the mixture at 60° for 80 h.

reaction. The rate constants were calculated on the basis of the least-square method and were reproducible with $\pm 3\%$.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying concentration of Complex-I on rate constant: In this set of experiment, the concentration of Complex-I was varied in the range 0.00125–0.005 M at a constant excess concentration of 0.05 M quinolinic acid. Ionic strength (0.5 M), pH (4) and temperature (55°) were also kept constant. At pH 4.0, $cis-[Cr(ox)_2(H_2O)_2]^-$ and $quinH^-$ are the reacting species. It was observed that the rate of reaction is first order with respect to Complex-I, i.e.

$$d[\text{Complex-II}]/dt = k_{obs}[\text{Complex-I}]$$

Effect of varying pH on rate constant: At fixed concentration of Complex-I (0.0025 M) and quinolinic acid (0.025 M) and at fixed ionic strength (0.5 M) and temperature (60°), pH was varied from 2.0 to 5.9. The results are presented in Table 1. At lower pH values, the reaction was slow due to decrease in $[quinH^-]$, a bidentate ligand. It is clear that lower the pH higher is the protonation of quinolinic anion and obviously the donor capability of the ligand to the metal ion is decreased, and consequently the rate is slowed down.

pK values of quinolinic acid, as shown in equations (1) and (2), indicate that at pH 3.4 and above,

quinolinic acid exists mainly as its anionic form. The pH dependence further indicates that the rate constant values pass through a maximum around pH 4.5 and again it decreases with the increase of pH. The substrate complex remains mainly in diaquo form at and below pH 6. As pH increases above 6, the substrate complex is converted into hydroxo complex, as shown in equations (3) and (4).

The hydroxide ion in hydroxo complex exerts electromeric effect which increases electron density on chromium and reduces the possibility of nucleophilic attack by quinolinic ion on reaction site. So rate constants should decrease with increase in pH above 6.0. Actually, rate constants decrease above pH 4.5. Above pH 4.5, $[quin^{2-}]$ increases and $[quinH^-]$ decreases according to equation (2). The increase in $[quin^{2-}]$ decreases the possibility of formation of activated complex, since increase in negative charge on the incoming ligand increases the repulsion between negatively charged substrate and incoming ligand, and reduces the rate. Thus in the pH range 2.0–5.9, the pseudo-first order rate constant of the reaction increases at first with increase of pH, reaches a maximum around 4.5 and then decreases.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH DIFFERENT pH

$[quinH^-] = 0.025 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Complex}] = 0.0025 \text{ M}$, Temp = 60°, Ionic strength = 0.5 M (NaClO₄)

pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
2.0	5.90	4.9	39.905
3.0	7.75	5.5	22.59
3.5	11.00	5.9	15.82
4.0	14.70		
4.5	46.40		

Effect of varying quinolinic acid concentration on rate constant: The concentration of quinolinic acid was varied in the range 0.025–0.065 M at a fixed concentration of Complex-I (0.0025 M), at 45, 50, 55, 60 and 65°. In these experiments, the ionic strength and pH were kept constant at 0.5 M and 4.0, respectively. The results presented in Table 2 show that the rate continuously increases with increasing $[quinH^-]$ at each temperature according to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = k_2[\text{Complex-I}][quinH^-] = k_{obs}[\text{Complex-I}]$$

where, k_2 is the second order rate constant and k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order rate constant. Fig. 2 shows the plots of $\log(D_\infty - D_0)/(D_\infty - D_t)$ against time in min. From the slope of this plot, k_{obs} can be

Fig. 2. Graphical presentation of k_{obs} (50°) at complex = 0.0025 M, pH = 4.0: [quinH⁻] = (A) 0.025, (B) 0.035, (C) 0.045 and (D) 0.055, and (E) 0.065 M.

Fig. 3. Dependence of k_{obs} on quinolate ion concentration at [Complex] = 0.0025 M, pH = 4.0: temperature (A) 45°, (B) 50°, (C) 55°, (D) = 60° and (E) = 65°.

evaluated. Values of k_{obs} were plotted against [quinH⁻] at different temperatures (45, 50, 55, 60 and 65°) as shown in Fig. 3; the slope of each

linear plot gave the corresponding value of k_2 , shown in Table 3. The linear dependence of rate on [quinH⁻] suggests that the reaction proceeds through associative path.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) WITH CONCENTRATION OF QUINOLINATE ION
[Complex-I] = 0.0025 M, Ionic strength = 0.5 M (NaClO₄), pH = 4.0

[quinH ⁻] M	k_{obs} ($\times 10^3$ min ⁻¹) at temp. (°C)				
	45	50	55	60	65
0.025	4.7	7.1	10.4	14.7	23.8
0.035	6.5	9.9	14.4	19.6	33.4
0.045	8.4	12.6	18.3	26.5	42.9
0.055	10.2	15.4	22.3	32.3	52.5
0.065	12.1	18.0	26.4	38.2	62.0

TABLE 3—VALUES OF SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ionic strength = 0.5 M (NaClO₄), pH = 4.0

k_2 ($\times 10^3$ min ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Temp. (°C)				
	45	50	55	60	65
	18.6	28.0	42.0	58.8	95.4

Influence of ionic strength on reaction rate: The ionic strength of the medium was varied by the addition of desired amount of NaClO₄ in the reaction medium. The pseudo-first order rate constants at 60° are 9.90×10^{-3} , 11.45×10^{-3} , 14.71×10^{-3} and 21.94×10^{-3} at ionic strengths 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.6 M, respectively at [Complex-I] = 0.0025 M, [Ligand] = 0.025 M and pH = 4.0.

The simple Debye-Huckel theory leads to the prediction that the rate of a reaction between similarly charged ions should increase with the increase in ionic strength of the medium as represented by the equation¹⁹,

$$\log k = \log k_0 + 2QZ_A Z_B \sqrt{\mu} \quad (5)$$

when the two reactants A and B are associated to form the activated complex. The present results are in conformity with equation (5) since increase in ionic strength of the medium increases the rate of the reaction. Thus associative mechanism for this anation reaction is supported.

Effect of temperature on rate constant: The effect of temperature on the rate constant was studied at different concentration of the ligand and the values of rate constants are given in Table 2. The activation parameters have been calculated from the plots of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$. The results reveal $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 17.46$ kcal mol⁻¹, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -15.5$ e.u.

Mechanism: The above results suggest that under the experimental conditions employed the reaction proceeds through the following mechanism,

S_N^2 path:

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

System	Rate const. at 25°	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	Ref.
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ^{-a} + quinolinic acid	5.7 × 10 ⁻⁴ ^c s ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	17.46	-15.5	This work
<i>cis</i> -[Cr(ox) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ⁻ + H ₂ O ^b (isotopic water exchange)	7.78 × 10 ⁻⁴ s ⁻¹	18.0	-21.6	20

^aThis work. ^bRef. 20. ^cExtrapolated value from Eyring plot.

This mechanism is supported by comparison of rate constant and activation parameters of quinolinic acid substitution with the corresponding parameter for water exchange process in *cis*-[Cr(ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ (Table 4).

It appears from Table 4 that rate of quinolinic acid substitution is faster than isotopic water-exchange rate at a common temperature. The activation enthalpy for quinolinic acid substitution is lower than the corresponding parameter for water-exchange process. These data indicate an associative character of the substitution process.

Associative mechanism for the quinolinic acid substitution is further supported by the effect of pH on reaction rate. At lower pH values, where the complex remains in diaquo form, the reaction is slow due to protonation of carboxylate ion of the ligand. The rate increases with increase of pH from 2 to 4.5 due to increased donor capability of quinH⁻ anion. With further increase of pH, though the complex remains in diaquo form, the rate decreases due to the formation of quin²⁻ anion in which distant carboxylate group can not coordinate to the central atom as is verified from examination of molecular model. The decrease in rate with increasing concentration of quin²⁻ is due to the increased electrostatic repulsion between the negatively charged substrate complex and incoming ligand in the formation of activated complex, *i.e.* in the formation of activated complex, quin²⁻ is less favoured as compared to quinH⁻. This fact supports associative nature of the activation process. Moreover, increase of rate with increase of ionic strength indicates according to equation (5) the associative nature of the substitution process.

Thus we can conclude that aquo ligand substitution in *cis*-[Cr(ox)₂(H₂O)₂]⁻ by quinolinic anion involves the formation of new metal-ligand bond

in transition state and the mechanism is associative in nature.

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References

1. R. E. HAMM and R. E. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3085.
2. R. E. HAMM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5670.
3. R. E. HAMM and R. H. PERKINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2083.
4. R. E. HAMM, R. L. JOHNSON, R. H. PERKINS and R. E. DAVIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4469.
5. D. BANERJEA and S. DUTTACHAUDHURI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 871.
6. D. BANERJEA and J. ROY, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1973, **399**, 115.
7. J. N. MANDAL and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **17**, 354.
8. J. N. MANDAL and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 580.
9. B. K. NIOGY and G. S. DE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sec.)*, 1983, **92**, 153.
10. M. BHATTACHARYYA and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 626.
11. T. W. KALLEN and E. SENKO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 2924.
12. H. KELM and G. M. HARRIES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 706.
13. O. SCHENK and H. KELM, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1972, **2**, 71.
14. C. CHATTERJEE and A. K. BASAK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, **16**, 758.
15. W. G. PALMFR, "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1954, p. 387.
16. K. V. KRISHNAMURTY and G. M. HARRIS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 213.
17. *Chem. Soc. Spec. Publ.*, 1964, **17**, 496.
18. C. SCHENK, H. STIEGER and H. KELM, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1972, **391**, 1.
19. K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", 2nd. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1965, p. 220.
20. H. STIEGER, G. M. HARRIES and H. KELM, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 262.